

**IMPLEMENTING PLANT DISEASE DETECTION SYSTEM USING
CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK (CNN)****Dr. G. PRIYANKA JEEVA KARUNYA**Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science Engineering,
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JNTUH College of Engineering Sultanpur, Telangana, India**ABSTRACT**

Agriculture plays a crucial role in global food security, but in plant disease can be reduce crop yield and quality. Traditional method of detecting plant diseases depends on manual inspection, which can be slow. Process of industry that required a large amount of labor to produce its goods or services. And offer requires the expertise of trained professional, In this project we propose a plant disease detection system using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). The system classifies plant diseases based on leaf images, providing a fast and accurate diagnosis. The model is trained on the Plant Village dataset, which contains images of various crops affected by different diseases. The proposed CNN model consists of multiple convolutional and pooling layers to extract features, followed by fully connected layers for classification. The system achieves high accuracy in identifying plant diseases, making it a valuable tool for farmers and agricultural experts. Additionally, we trained the model can be development on mobile applications, web platforms, or IoT devices, allowing real-time disease detection in the field. The study also explores transfer learning techniques to improve performance and reduce training time. The proposed system helps in early disease detection, reducing crop losses, and promoting sustainable farming practices.

Keywords:

Deep Learning, CNN, Plant Disease Detection, Image Classification, Smart Agriculture, transfer Learning.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is one of the oldest and most vital methods of ensuring food security. It serves as a vital source of income for people worldwide. After all, food is fundamental to human survival, and no one can live without it. Plants play a crucial role—not only as a food source for humans but also for animals. Governments and agricultural experts are taking significant initiatives. In continually work to enhance food production through diverse projects and advancements. we are facing major challenges in our farmers. When a plant is infected, it doesn't just affect the crop—it can have a effect on the entire environment. this disease can be affected various parts, like leaf's, branch and stems and etc..., Even the types of illnesses fungal that impacts plants such as bacterial, inserts and fungal disease etc., farmers. It is essential to utilize appropriate pesticides. Over time, considerable research efforts have focused on supporting farmers through technological advancements. While experienced farmers can often identify plant diseases visually, this usually happens at later stages of infection or when crop yield noticeably drops. To address this, modern technology is being utilized to detect plant diseases early, helping farmers keep track of crop health more effectively. These tools are beneficial for both small and large-scale agricultural operations, providing accurate and rapid results. This system leverages Deep Learning and Neural Networks to explore plant health. The Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model is trained on a dataset comprising images of healthy leaves as well as those affected by diseases. Once the model is trained, it can swiftly and accurately determine the condition of a plant based on an image of its leaf, facilitating timely intervention and improved crop management. The objective is to create a plant disease detection system utilizing CNN-based techniques to accurately classify and identify various plant diseases from leaf images, with the system designed to be user-friendly. Once trained, the model can quickly and accurately identify the condition of a plant based on an image of its leaf—enabling timely intervention and better crop management.

aims to develop a plant disease detection system using CNN-based techniques to accurately classify and detect various plant disease detection from leaf images, Farmers may take pictures of impacted.

OBJECTIVES

The aim of this project to identify the plant disease detection using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), In this we design to implement a CNN of Deep learning model to detect. In this, we used the CNN to preprocess other images in order to increase the model's generalization and classification accuracy. In this we are taking real-time dataset to train high quality images of both healthy and diseased plant leaves to high accuracy of disease types using CNN.

METHODOLOGY

A convolutional neural network is a form of Artificial neural network is attended to process pixel input and is used in image recognition plant disease detection system using convolutional neural network(CNN). In this process is divided several stages, data acquisition, preprocessing, model development, training and validation, and development. to development of CNN system to capable of autonomously to identifying the categorizing plant disease detection using System to leaf's images utilizing the deep learning techniques. To approach to gather the high-quality images dataset to perform to plant disease preprocessing to dataset to improve the efficacy of the model. Creating a taring model a convolution neural network (CNN). To implementing the model for real-time application. [B4.1]

- **DATA COLLECTION:** - we collect images from publicly accessible datasets, including plant village, Kaggle datasets and various academic repositories. In datasets, images are gathered of both healthy and diseased leaves from various crop types, including tomatoes and potatoes, as well as different categories of datasets. In all images provides in .jpg or .png formats, featuring a variety of resolutions.
- **DATA PREPROCESSING:** All image were resized to a fixed dimension.
- Example: 224*224 pixels.
- **NORMALIZATION:** Pixel values were scaled to the range [0, 1] by dividing by 255. - Data Augmentation: Rotation, flipping, zooming, brightness, etc.

FEATURE EXTRACTION:

CONVOLUTION LAYER: These layers apply Convolutional operations assist in maintaining the spatial relationships among pixels. [4]

ACTIVATION LAYER: : An activation layer is a component of a neural network that applies an activation function to the output of each neuron. This function transforms the weighted sum of inputs into an output signal that can be passed to the next layer. The primary purpose of an activation layer is to introduce non-linearity into the model, allowing it to learn and represent complex relationships in the data. [5].

POOLING LAYER: This layer is periodically inserted in the convnets and its main function is to reduce the size of volume which makes the computation fast reduces memory and also prevents overfitting. Two types of pooling layers are max pooling and average pooling. If we use a max pool with 2 x 2 filters and stride 2, the resultant volume will be of dimension 16x16x12.

FLATTENING LAYER: The Flatten layer within Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) serves the purpose of transforming multi-dimensional data (such as 2D feature maps) into a one-dimensional array.

DROPOUT LAYER: Dropout layers are technique used in neural networks to reduce overfitting, which occurs when a model memorizes training data instead of learning general patterns.

DENSE LAYER: A dense layer, sometimes referred to as completely linked layer, is a basic component of neural networks. In dense layer, each neuron receives input from every neuron in the preceding layer. This means that every neuron in the dense layer has a connection, and weight associated with every neuron in the previous layer, allowing the layer to learn complex relationships between the input features.

FULLY CONNECTED LAYERS: These layers are responsible for making predictions based on the high-level features learned by previous layers. They have created a fully connected layer.

OUTPUT LAYER: The output layer in deep learning model is the final layer that produces the model's predictions

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The plant disease detection system was developed using CNN model, trained and tested in Python with the help of libraries like TensorFlow and Keres. The dataset used consisted of labeled images of healthy and diseased plant leaves from multiple crops, primarily sourced from the Plant Village dataset.

MODEL TRAINING: The CNN model was trained for 5/5 epochs. using split for training, validation and testing sets. Data augmentation techniques like rotation, flipping, and zooming were applied to the training data to prevent overfitting.

PERFORMANCE METRICS:

Accuracy: The model achieved an overall accuracy of approximately 98% on the test dataset, indicating strong performance in correctly classifying various plant diseases and healthy leaves.

Precision and Recall: The precision and recall scores for most disease classes were above 90%, showing the model's effectiveness in minimizing false positives and false negatives.

Confusion Matrix: The confusion matrix demonstrated that the model sometimes confused visually similar diseases, such as early blight and late blight in tomatoes, but overall classification was highly accurate.

Visualization: Training and validation accuracy and loss curves showed steady improvement with minimal over fitting, confirming the effectiveness of data augmentation and proper training strategies. Sample test images were accurately classified, showcasing the practical utility of the model.

Hardware and Training Time : Training was conducted on a system equipped with a GPU, requiring around 10 minutes and 8 seconds to finish 5 out of 5 epochs. Resizing the images to 124×124 pixels struck a favorable balance between computational efficiency and the preservation of model accuracy.

Graphs:

OUTPUT SCREEN:

Plant Disease Detection System Using CNN

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CONCLUSION

In this project, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based system was developed using Python to identify and categorize plant diseases from leaf images. The model showed high accuracy in detecting various plant diseases, thanks to deep learning's ability to automatically learn and extract complex features from images. Using a well-prepared dataset, proper preprocessing, and data augmentation techniques, the system achieved reliable performance across various disease categories. The utilization of Python libraries like TensorFlow, Keras, and Open CV facilitated the effective development and evaluation of the model.

The results highlight CNNs as a powerful and practical solution for automated plant disease detection, which can help farmers and agricultural experts take timely action and reduce crop loss. This system can be further enhanced by using real-time image input from mobile devices or drones, integrating metadata such as location and weather conditions, and applying the model to more diverse and larger datasets. Overall, the project demonstrates

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